

DOMINANT FACTORS AFFECTING THE SUSTAINABILITY PROFESSIONALISM OF FILM ACTORS THROUGH PROFESSIONAL ORGANIZATION

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Abstract

This study seeks to examine whether competence, education, regulatory implementation, and industrial relations are dominant factors influencing the realization of sustainable professionalism among actors/film actors through the role of professional organizations. The research employed an explanatory quantitative approach and hypothesis testing, and data analysis was conducted using the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM-AMOS) method. The sample consisted of 171 film/television actors in the Jakarta metropolitan area, selected through random sampling, including both those affiliated with and those not affiliated with professional organizations. The findings indicated that competence and education were dominant factors that directly influenced sustainable professionalism, as they had a positive and significant impact. However, they did show a significant impact when mediated by the role of professional organizations. Regulatory implementation and industrial relations had a positive and significant effect on the role of professional organizations, but did not directly influence sustainable professionalism. Furthermore, the study also found that the role of professional organizations did not significantly influence sustainable professionalism, indicating that their mediating role in supporting human resource development within the film industry is not yet optimal. As a managerial implication, this study suggests that professional organizations need to develop operational policies to measurably improve the competence and education of their members in order to enhance sustainable professionalism.

Keywords: Competence, Education, Industrial Relations, Continuous Professionalism, Professional Organization.

INTRODUCTION

In the realm of culture, cinema is not merely a medium of entertainment, but also a for expressing values, identity, and human struggles within the social sphere. As central figures in cinematic works, actors aesthetic and ethical responsibilities in portraying human narratives on screen. However, behind the symbolism and popularity associated with an actor's persona lies a structural issue: the development of sustainable professionalism has not been fully established. Additionally, ICT's rapid advancement and development have significantly transformed the film industry.

Films that were once exclusively accessible in cinemas are now widely available through various digital platforms, allowing audiences to enjoy entertainment anytime and anywhere via television or mobile devices (e.g., YouTube, Vidio, TikTok, etc.). On the other hand, actors' legacy rights in the entertainment industry have not been adequately protected. This is believed to be due to the absence of a system that safeguards the sustainability of their professions, one

contributing factor being the suboptimal human capital management within the film industry's professional organizations.

Human capital management plays a vital role in the success of a professional organization. Fauzia et al (2017) argue that human resources are an active asset that serves to optimize other organizational resources. In today's rapid scientific and technological advancement era, the global competitive landscape demands that organizations cultivate innovative and responsive human capable of adapting to ongoing developments. According to Mahdavi et al. (2023), technological progress and environmental changes have positioned human resources as a key factor for organizational leaders seeking to compete and achieve a sustainable competitive advantage.

Sustainable professionalism is a continuous professional practice maintained throughout an individual's career by keeping pace with the rapid and ongoing developments in science and technology. It ensures that one's skills, knowledge, and experience remain aligned with the dynamic changes of the times (Megginson, 2003). As outlined earlier, the challenges and issues faced by human resources in the film industry are primarily related to the growing demand for sustainable professionalism among actors.

This behavior is considered a key contributor to achieving competitive advantage within the film industry. Therefore, it is essential to develop and nurture professionalism among film actors. Theoretically, numerous factors influence the and development of professional behavior among actors, including educational background, competencies, experience, training, government regulations, the role of professional organizations, knowledge, compensation, organizational climate, industrial relations, etc.

Previous studies on professionalism include Budiningsih's (2023) research on the relationship between human capital and training on managerial professionalism, which showed a positive and very strong correlation, contributing 79.3% to the achievement of professionalism. Other studies also extensively conducted the influence of competence and education on the professionalism of actors (Piwowar-Sulej, 2021; Grin et al., 2021; Lozano et al., 2017), However, there remains limited research on the influence of regulatory frameworks, industrial relations, and professional organizations on the sustainable professionalism of actors, particularly film actors.

Based on the discussions, this study aims to examine several factors that are believed to significantly influence the sustainable professionalism of film actors, specifically competence, education, regulation implementation, and industrial relations through the mediating role of professional organizations.

Thus, the research questions addressed in this study include:

- a) Do competence, education, regulatory implementation, and industrial relations influence the role of professional organizations?
- b) Do competence, education, regulatory implementation, and industrial relations influence sustainable professionalism?
- c) Does the role of professional organizations influence sustainable professionalism?
- d) Do competence, education, implementation of regulations, and industrial relations influence sustainable professionalism through the role of professional organizations?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Competence

Competence, often referred to as skill, is a person's ability to perform a job and is influenced by various personal characteristics and traits. Individuals with work-related competencies are more likely to complete their tasks effectively. According to Wiek et al. (2011), competencies include the knowledge, cognitive abilities, and practical skills required to initiate, facilitate, apply, or contribute to transformations toward sustainability. Budiningsih et al. (2017) explain that competence refers to an individual's work ability, encompassing the following aspects: a) knowledge, b) skills, and c) work attitude, all of which reflect personal characteristics, self-concept, and values applicable across a wide range of situations and sustained over time. Similarly, Zhang et al. (2016), support Budiningsih's view by stating that competencies are comprehensive capabilities that include knowledge, skills, and attitudes used to solve various problems in specific contexts. Furthermore, Devos et al. (2015) emphasize that competencies should be developed, organized, and presented appropriately and measurably to ensure they can be optimally utilized in an individual's career development (devos et al., 2015).

Based on the description mentioned above, competence in this study refers to the personal characteristics that underlie and facilitate an actor's outstanding performance. It includes: a) knowledge, b) skills, and c) attitudes possessed by actors in order to remain competitive in the film industry, both nationally and internationally.

Education

In Indonesia, education is regulated by Law No. 20 of 2003 and is categorized into: a) formal education; b) non-formal education; and c) informal education. Formal education refers to a structured and tiered system that includes primary, secondary, and higher education. Non-formal education is an alternative pathway outside the formal system that can be implemented in a structured and hierarchical manner. Meanwhile, informal education is a learning process carried out by families and communities in the form of independent learning activities. Various training programs that serve as strengthening instruments generally support optimal educational outcomes. According to Hasan (2015), education and training are processes to create an environment in which human resources (HR) can acquire or develop the attitudes, skills, expertise, knowledge, and behaviors relevant to their work.

According to Nurpianti et al. (2019), continuous education encourages learners to think critically, envision a more positive and sustainable future, and develop the ability to solve problems within their environment.

Based on the description, education in this study refers to the process of continuous learning and development that enables individuals to fulfill their responsibilities as lifelong learners. It encompasses three main forms: a) formal education, b) non-formal education, and c) informal education.

Regulatory Implementation

Drahos (2017) states that regulation is a rule or mechanism that restricts, guides, or controls social behavior. Similarly, according to Lodge and Wegrich (2012), regulation is a continuous and focused effort to change the behavior of others in accordance with established standards and objectives. This may involve mechanisms such as standard-setting, information gathering, and behavioral modification. Furthermore, Baldwin et al. (2012) and Drahos (2017) state that

there are three main functions of regulation: a) responsiveness, b) protection, and c) enforcement of compliance. Thus, implementing regulation can be understood as enforcing laws or regulations where actors, organizations, procedures, and techniques collaborate to achieve a given policy or program (Wiyani & Barnawi, 2012).

Based on the above description, the implementation of regulations refers to the government's intervention through various efforts and means to control, guide, and direct societal behavior in order to establish a professional, fair, and sustainable work ecosystem. Such regulations must contain the following characteristics: a) responsiveness; b) protection; and c) community compliance in their implementation.

Industrial Relations

According to Ariani (2014), industrial relations are interactions between industrial actors that produce various binding rules in the workplace. These rules originate from interactions between employers and employees, resulting in internal company regulations, such as collective labor agreements and customary practices recognized by both parties. Furthermore, Ariani (2014) explains that these rules may be applied individually or through their representatives in employee organizations, and such rules only apply to members of those organizations. Meanwhile, according to Bappenas-USAID (2002), optimal industrial relations include the following indicators: a) intensive dialogue (interaction); b) equality; c) freedom of expression.

Hence, the term “industrial relations” in this study refers to interactions among industrial actors that result in harmonious and binding labor relationships between employers/management, the government, and workers. These relationships are characterized by: a) intensive dialogue, b) equality, and c) freedom of expression among members.

The Role of Professional Organizations

A professional organization is an association of individuals engaged in the same profession, established to enhance and develop professional standards, uphold ethical conduct, pursue shared goals within the field, and safeguard mutual interests. According to Brock & Saks (2016) and Walsh and Daddario (2015), professional organizations typically have the following characteristics: a) there is generally only one recognized professional organization within a specific region (local, national, or international); b) they operate based on a defined code of ethics, standards of professional competencies, service quality benchmark, and guidelines for education and training, while also advocating for professional autonomy. Furthermore, Breckon et al. (1998) outline the roles of professional organizations as follows: a) developing and advancing the profession; b) regulating and expanding the scope of the profession; c) consolidating the opinions of professional members; d) providing platforms members participation; and e) actively contributing to the continuous progress of the profession.

Thus, the role of professional organizations in this study refers to practitioner-based -based institutions that serve to protect, develop, and advocate for their members' interests through competency standardization, policy advocacy, rights protection, and capacity building. These organizations function as professional service providers, including: a) developing and advancing the profession; b) expanding the scope of action; c) consolidating opinions; and d) facilitating access to work opportunities.

Sustainable Professionalism

According to the United Nations (2010), professionalism is a core human resources, characterized by the capabilities to work calmly, competently, and with commitment to an institution. Salovaara (2022), sustainable professionalism is based on ideals that appear to contradict or conflict with the values and norms in some sectors where sustainability is applied.

Meanwhile, Morrow & Goetz (1988) argue that indicators of sustainable professionalism include: a) dedication to the profession, demonstrated through the application of knowledge and skills; b) social commitment to society; c) independence, reflected in the capacity for decision-making; d) self-regulation, which involves evaluating the work performed; and e) the development of collaborative relationships with partners.

Based on the earlier description, sustainable professionalism in film actors refers to their ability to consistently maintain work quality, uphold professional ethics, ensure career sustainability, and the relevance of their competencies amid industry changes, as evidenced by: a) dedication; b) social commitment; c) independence; d) self-regulation; and e) maintaining relationships with partners in pursuing their work.

Based on the analysis of the literature review above, it is suspected that professional organizations positively influence competence, education, regulatory implementation, and industrial relations in the achievement of sustainable professionalism among film actors. Accordingly, the research hypotheses are as follows:

- H1: There is a positive and significant influence of competence, education, regulatory implementation, and industrial relations on the role of professional organizations.
- H2: There is a positive and significant influence of competence, education, regulatory implementation, and industrial relations on sustained professionalism.
- H3: There is a positive and significant influence of the role of professional organizations on sustained professionalism.
- H4: There is a significant influence of competence, education, regulatory implementation, and industrial relations on sustained professionalism through the role of professional organizations.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study aims to analyze the influence of competence (x1), education (x2), regulatory implementation (x3), and industrial relations (x4) on sustainable professionalism (y2), with the role of professional organizations (y1) as a mediating variable. The research design employs an explanatory quantitative approach and hypothesis testing through data analysis using the structural equation modeling (SEM-AMOS) method.

This method examines the influence of exogenous variables, competence, education, regulatory implementation, and industrial relations on the endogenous variable of sustainable professionalism, with the role of professional organizations serving as the mediating variable. The research design diagram is presented in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Participants and Data Collection

The respondents in this study consisted of 171 film and soap opera actors in the city of Jakarta, selected using random sampling. The sampling included both actors who were members of professional organizations and those who were not. According to Hair et al (2006), the appropriate sample size for data analysis using SEM is around 100-200 respondents. Thus, this study's sample size of 171 respondents meets the recommended criteria. Data was collected using a questionnaire administered to the film actors, employing a 5-point Likert scale: 5 = Strongly Agree; 4 = Agree; 3 = Neutral; 2 = Disagree; and 1 = Strongly Disagree. The author developed the questionnaire instrument through a literature review analysis. Prior to this use in the study, the instrument was tested for validity and reliability using a trial involving 30 participants. The validity test employed the Pearson correlation coefficient (r -product moment), the reliability test used the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient. The instrument was considered valid if the calculated $r \geq 0.361$ and reliable if the calculated $r \geq 0.6$ (Sugiyono, 2017). The research variables and indicators, as well as the results of the validity and reliability tests of the instrument, are presented in Tables 1 and 2 below:

Table 1: Variables and Indicators of Research Instruments

No	Variables	Indicators
1	Sustainable Professionalism (Y_1)	Dedication, social commitment, independence, self-regulation, and relationships with partners.
2	The Role of Professional Organizations (Y_2)	Professional development, opportunities to work, expanding the scope of action, and gathering opinions.
3	Competency (X_1)	Skill, knowledge and attitude
4	Education (X_2)	Formal education, non-formal education, and informal education.
5	Regulatory Implementation (X_3)	Responsive, protective, and compliant.
6	Industrial relations (X_4)	Intensive dialogue, equality, and freedom of expression.

Source: Primary data processed, 2025

Table 2: Test Results of Validity & Reliability of Research Instruments

No	Variable	Valid Instruments	r-Product Moment ($r \geq 0.361$)	Reliability Coefficient (Alpha-Cronbach)	Description
1	Sustainable Professionalism (Y_2)	26	0,460 - 0,960	0,898	Valid and reliable
2	The Role of Professional Organizations (Y_1)	25	0,740 – 0,950	0,978	Valid and reliable
3	Competency (X_1)	14	0,700 – 0,890	0,912	Valid and reliable
4	Education (X_2)	6	0,800 – 0,960	0,634	Valid and reliable
5	Regulatory Implementation (X_3)	13	0,610 – 0,870	0,861	Valid and reliable
6	Industrial Relations (X_4)	12	0,53 – 0,76	0,829	Valid and reliable

Source: Primary data processed, 2025

Data Analysis

Data analysis using the SEM approach was conducted to analyze the influence of exogenous variables, namely competence, education, regulatory implementation, and industrial relations, on the endogenous variable of sustainable professionalism, with the role of professional organizations acting as a mediating variable. The measurement model analysis in SEM used Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) based on the developed model. Model fit was evaluated using Goodness of Fit indices, which included Chi-Square, CMIN/DF, RMSEA, GFI, and TLI statistics.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Respondent Profile

Figure 2: Results of the Analysis

In general, the profile of the research respondents includes the following: 62% are male and 38% are female respondents. Based on age distribution, 12% are aged 25-35, 25% are aged 36-45, and 63% are over 45.

In terms of work experience: 12% have 5-10 years of experience, 27% have 11-20 years of experience, and 61% have more than 20 years of experience.

Regarding educational background, 34% have a high school diploma, 21% have an associate's degree, and 45% have a bachelor's degree.

The complete results of the SEM analysis are presented in figure 2 below:

The complete statistical analysis results are presented in Figure 2 above and explained as follows:

The Influence of Competence, Education, Regulatory Implementation, and Industrial Relations on the Role of Professional Organizations

The results of the SEM analysis examining the influence of competence, education, regulatory implementation, and industrial relations on the role of professional organizations are presented in Table 3 below:

Table 3: Results of The Influence of Competence, Education, Regulatory Implementation, And Industrial Relations on the Role of Professional Organizations.

Exogenous Variables	Endogenous Variables	Standardized Regression Weight	Estimate	SE	C.R.	P	Description
Competency (X ₁)	The Role of Professional Organizations (Y ₁)	0.153	0.223	0.430	0.519	0.129	Not Influential
Education (X ₂)	The Role of Professional Organizations (Y ₁)	0.122	0.172	0.429	0.401	0.689	Not Influential
Regulatory Implementation (X ₃)	The Role of Professional Organizations (Y ₁)	0.383	0.453	0.081	5.573	0.000	Influential
Industrial Relations (X ₄)	The Role of Professional Organizations (Y ₁)	0.350	0.400	0.107	3.745	0.000	Influential

Source: Primary data processed, 2025

Based on Table 3, the analysis reveals that the variables of competence (X₁) and education (X₂) do not significantly influence the role of professional organizations (Y₁). In contrast, regulatory implementation (X₃) and industrial relations (X₄) show a positive and significant influence on the role of organizations (Y₁). This conclusion is supported by the critical ratio (CR) values exceeding 2 (> 2) and the p-value being below 0.05 (< 0.05). Specifically, the standardized regression weight for the competence variable (X₁) is 0.153 and for education (X₂) is 0.122. This indicates that competence (X₁) and education (X₂) do not have a positive and significant influence on the role of professional organizations (Y₁). Meanwhile, the standardized regression weight coefficient values for the regulation implementation (X₃) variable are 0.383, and for industrial relations (X₄) are 0.350, with CR values also greater than 2 (> 2) and p-values < 0.05 . This indicates that regulatory implementation (X₃) and industrial relations (X₄) have a positive and significant effect on the role of professional organizations (Y₁). In this case, it can be concluded that H₁: there is no effect between competence and

education on professional organizations, but regulatory implementation and industrial relations have a positive and significant effect on the role of organizations.

The Effect of Competence, Education, Regulatory Implementation, and Industrial Relations on Sustainable Professionalism

The results of the SEM analysis regarding the influence of competence, education, regulatory implementation, and industrial relations on sustainable professionalism are presented in Table 4 below:

Table 4: The effect of competence, education, regulatory implementation, and industrial relations on sustainable professionalism.

Exogenous Variables	Endogenous Variables	Standardized Regression Weight	Estimate	SE	C.R.	P	Description
Competency (X ₁)	Sustainable Professionalism (Y ₂)	0.653	0.723	0.109	6.633	0.000	Influential
Education (X ₂)	Sustainable Professionalism (Y ₂)	0.423	0.493	0.123	4.013	0.000	Influential
Regulatory Implementation (X ₃)	Sustainable Professionalism (Y ₂)	0.092	0.142	0.345	0.412	0.681	Not Influential
Industrial Relations (X ₄)	Sustainable Professionalism (Y ₂)	0.081	0.131	0.522	0.251	0.802	Not Influential

Source: Primary data processed, 2025

Based on Table 4 above, the variables of competence (X₁) and education (X₂) have a positive and significant effect on sustainable professionalism (Y₂). This is evidenced by CR values greater than 2 (> 2), namely 6.633 and 4.013, and the p-value is less than 0.05 (< 0.05), with standardized regression weight coefficients of 0.653 for competence (X₁) and 0.423 for education (X). Meanwhile, the variables of regulatory implementation (X₃) and industrial relations (X₄) show standardized regression weight coefficients of only 0.092 and 0.081, respectively. Their p-values are greater than 0.05 (> 0.05), and the CR values are below 2 (< 2). This indicates that regulatory implementation (X₃) and industrial relations (X₄) do not have a significant influence on sustainable professionalism (Y₂). Therefore, it can be concluded that for H₂, competence and education only influence sustainable professionalism, while regulatory implementation and industrial relations do not.

The Influence of Professional Organization on Sustainable Professionalism

The results of the SEM analysis of the influence of professional organizations on sustainable professionalism are presented in Table 5 below:

Table 5: The influence of professional organizations on sustainable professionalism

Variable Exogenous	Variable Endogenous	Standardized Regression Weight	Estimate	SE	C.R.	P	Description
The Role of Professional Organizations (Y ₁)	Sustainable Professionalism (Y ₂)	0.051	0.121	0.112	0.1079	0.281	Not Influential

Source: Primary data processed, 2025

Based on Table 5, of the role of professional organization (Y1) is shown to have no significant effect on sustainable professionalism (Y). This is evidenced by the critical ratio (CR) value of only 0.1079 (< 2), p-value of 0.281 (> 0.05), and the standardized regression weight coefficient value of only 0.051. These values demonstrate that the influence of professional organizations on sustainable professionalism is neither positive nor statistically significant. Therefore, Hypothesis 3H3, which states that the role of professional organizations has an effect on sustainable professionalism, is not proven and must be rejected.

The influence of competence, education, regulatory implementation, and industrial relations on sustainable professionalism through the role of professional organizations.

The results of the analysis of the influence of competence, education, regulatory implementation, and industrial relations on sustainable professionalism through the role of professional organizations are presented in Table 6 below:

Table 6: The influence of competence, education, regulatory implementation, and industrial relations on sustainable professionalism through the role of professional organizations.

Variable Exogenous	Variable Mediation	Variable Endogenous	Direct influence	Indirect influence	Total influence	Description
Competency (X ₁)	The Role of Professional Organizations (Y ₁)	Sustainable Professionalism (Y ₂)	0.653	0.153 x 0.051 = 0.007	0.66	Mediation
Education (X ₂)	The Role of Professional Organizations (Y ₁)	Sustainable Professionalism (Y ₂)	0.423	0.122 x 0.051 = 0.006	0.429	Mediation
Regulatory Implementation (X ₃)	The Role of Professional Organizations (Y ₁)	Sustainable Professionalism (Y ₂)	0.092	0.383 x 0.051 = 0.019	0.111	Mediation
Industrial Relations (X ₄)	The Role of Professional Organizations (Y ₁)	Sustainable Professionalism (Y ₂)	0.081	0.350 x 0.051 = 0.017	0.098	Mediation

Source: Primary data processed, 2025

Based on Table 6, the role of professional organizations (Y1) functions as an effective intervening variable that mediates the influence of competence (X1), education (X2), regulatory implementation (X3), and industrial relations on sustainable professionalism (Y2). This is evidenced by the total influence value greater than the respective direct influence (see detailed in Table 6). Among these variables, the mediating strength (intervening) for the competency (X1) and education (X2) variables is stronger compared to the regulatory implementation (X3) and industrial relations (X4) variables.

These findings support Hypothesis 4 (H4), indicating that the role of organizations has a statistically significant mediating effect. In other words, competence, education, regulation implementation, and industrial relations influence sustainable professionalism through the role of professional organizations. Thus, it can be concluded that H4 is accepted: the role of professional organizations serves as an effective mediator in linking core professional development factors to sustainable professionalism.

Goodness of fit

Figure 3: Goodness of Fit

Table 7: Hasil Pengujian Goodness of Fit Model Struktural

<i>Goodness of Fit</i>	<i>Cut-Off Value</i>	Model Result	Description
Chi-Square (df=94)	142.11	349.40	Marginal
<i>Probability Chi-Square</i>	≥ 0.05	0.001	Marginal
CMIN/DF	≤ 2.00	2.010	Marginal
RMSEA	≤ 0.08	0.079	Fulfil
GFI	≥ 0.90	0.901	Fulfil
TLI	≥ 0.95	0.922	Fulfil

Source: Primary data processed, 2025

DISCUSSION

The results of Soehari et al's (2022) research at Bank Indonesia show that the organization is a very weak factor in supporting the strengthening of professionalism. As such, organizational capital is not a strategic factor for enhancing professionalism among Bank Indonesia employees; it merely serves as a supporting factor. This finding aligns with the present study, which reveals that the role of professional organizations, especially for actors, remains ineffective in providing development and advocacy. Similarly, studies by Intan Cahya Kurniasari et. al. (2018), Jack Henry Syauta et. al. (2012), and Lies Putriana et. al. (2015) also conclude that organizational involvement does not lead to increased professionalism. The film industry has yet to fully implement competency-related governance due to the lack of technical training, continuing education, and certification based on national or international competency standards. This has resulted in a quality gap between actors in the Indonesian film industry. The issue directly affects productivity and work quality while creating inequality in working relationships between film actors, production houses, and other stakeholders. Existing

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regulations regarding worker competence in the film industry are merely advisory and not considered essential requirements. The lack of professional organizations further compounds this problem, undermining not only the quality of films but also hindering professionalism, production efficiency, and the industry's sustainability.

Education as the foundation of film professionalism serves as a strategic instrument in shaping the competence, ethics, and adaptability of film industry actors. In the context of film actors, education is not only limited to artistic acting skills, but also covers technical aspects, work culture, professional communication, and understanding of the film industry. However, in practice, the formal and non-formal education systems in Indonesia have yet to provide a structured, equitable, and industry-relevant educational pathway. This shortcoming is further worsened by the underperformance of professional organizations in supporting these educational efforts. The Indonesian film industry is governed by various regulations that seek to create a fair, competent, and professional work ecosystem. However, many of these regulations have not been effectively implemented, especially in regulating industrial relations between actors (as labor) and producers (as employers). As one of the main subjects in the film industry, actors often find themselves in vulnerable positions: lacking standardized work contracts, receiving non-standard wages, facing excessive working hours, and having no access to employment-related social security. This highlights the crucial role of film professional organizations becomes crucial as a bridge between regulations and real-world implementation.

In industrial relations, there are several complex issues, including the unclear legal status and working relationships of actors, the weak role of professional organizations as industrial liaisons, the lack of integration of regulations and employment systems, the absence of ethical standards and industrial codes of conduct, the power imbalances in working relationships, the disconnect between competence, certification, and professional recognition, and the absence of a sustainable industrial relations model. The presence of a professional organization should serve to protect and provide advocacy for its members. However, field findings reveal that respondents have not experienced such support. In many cases, actors or performers in films and soap operas face legal problems related to employment, such as delayed payments, harassment, lack of social protection, or unreasonable working hours. these are often resolved privately, without any involvement from professional organizations. This problem arised due to: a) the absence of a permanent legal unit or legal aid center in professional organizations, leaving actors feeling unsafe to report cases due to the organization's lack of responsiveness or independence; b) the lack of a credible system for reporting ethical and labor violations; c) the underdeveloped efforts in establishing and enforcing standardize contract and ethical standards. Many production houses continue to draft their contracts without consulting professional organizations. There is no structured system for monitoring or sanctioning ethical violations; d) the failure to empower professional organizations as regulatory partners. These organizations are still minimally involved in implementing labor and film regulations, and the government has yet to engage them in policy design or industrial supervision formally. Respondents reported the absence of a continuous career development process facilitated by professional organizations. Thus, in order to address this, it is essential to implement structured professional development programs focused on enhancing skills and knowledge, enabling actors to gain new experiences. This gap stems from the organization's failure to function as a catalyst in career advancement, its inability to foster professional solidarity and collective identity, and its lack of digital innovation and adaptation to the industry's evolving demands.

Managerial Implications

The findings of this study offer several strategic and practical implications for film actors as part of the core profession in the Indonesian film industry. These implications emphasize the critical role actors can play in realizing sustainable professionalism by strengthening the aspects of competence, education, implementation of regulations, industrial relations, with maximum support from professional organizations as a prerequisite for fostering a healthy and professional film industry ecosystem. Nevertheless, several key actions must be prioritized: first, increasing actor competence independently and collectively. Second, participation in continuing education and training. Third, advocacy for the implementation of regulations that favor the actor profession. Fourth, strengthening healthy and collective industrial relations. Fifth, professional organizations should be encouraged to be active and critical. Actors have a strategic position in improving the role of professional organizations to be more than symbolic. Actors need to be involved in the structure of professional organizations, both as administrators and active members who voice the needs of the field. With this involvement, professional organizations can be transformed into institutions that encourage training, mediation of work disputes, defense of professional rights, and development of ethical standards. Therefore, professional organizations such as PARFI (Indonesian Film Artists Association) can study and learn from good professional organizations such as IDI (Indonesian Doctors Association). Sixth, build a consistent image of professionalism in the public sphere and industry.

CONCLUSION

The professionalism of actors cannot rely solely on talent or experience. It must be reinforced by a systematic framework that ensures continuous learning, job protection, and a healthy and fair industrial ecosystem. In this context, sustainable professionalism is not merely an individual pursuit but a shared responsibility. Professional organizations, governments, educational institutions, and industry stakeholders all play vital roles in cultivating this ecosystem. As reflected in the variables explored in this study, including competence, education, implementation of regulations and industrial relations, the path toward sustainable actor professionalism requires a collaborative and integrated effort. This study presents four key findings. First, competence and education were found to have no significant effect on the role of professional organizations, whereas regulatory implementation and industrial relations significantly influenced the role of professional organizations. This indicates that out of four exogenous variables, only two demonstrated a measurable impact on professional. Second, there was no direct positive influence between regulatory implementation and industrial relations on sustainable professionalism. In contrast, competence and education were shown to influence sustainable professionalism positively. Third, the role of professional organizations did not have a significant direct effect on sustainable professionalism in the Indonesian film industry. Fourth, the role of professional organizations influences or is able to mediate competence, education, regulatory implementation, industrial relations towards sustainable professionalism. Therefore, it is important to encourage systemic transformation through inclusive policies, strengthen the role of professional organizations, and increase actors' awareness of the importance of continuous self-development. It is hoped that improvements in all sectors in the Indonesian film industry will lead to a professional, fair, integrated and sustainable film ecosystem, with actors as art workers who are legally protected, technically competent and develop in a standardized work system with improvements in all sectors so that the Indonesian film industry can operate in a structured, systematic and massive manner.

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